

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND STRAIN INDUCED CRYSTALLIZATION OF NBR COMPOSITES WITH DIFFERENT SURFACE TREATMENTS AND CONTENT OF CARBON NANO-TUBE

Jong Hwan Sung, Sang Ryeoul Ryu, and Dong Joo Lee*
 School of Mechanical Engineering, Yeungnam University, Gyungsan, Korea
 * Corresponding author (djlee@yu.ac.kr)

Keywords: *Atmospheric Pressure Flame Plasma Treatment, Acid Treatment, Carbon Nano-Tube, Elastomeric Composite, Differential Scanning Calorimetry*

1. Introduction

Since the discovery of carbon nano tube (CNT) by Iijima [1], it has become a potential candidate for a wide range of applications such as nanoelectronics, composite fabrication and gas storage. Extensive researches have been done by incorporating different types of CNTs as nanoreinforcements, nanowires and nanoconductors into polymeric materials to form new composites that possess high mechanical strength, electrical and thermal conductivities [2]. While CNTs have been widely used with different kinds of polymers, very little work has been done on incorporating CNTs in the rubber [2-4].

The classical methods available for evaluating the degree of cross-linking in elastomers are stress-strain and swelling measurements. A differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) is a convenient and rapid technique for the study of elastomer thermal characteristics [5-6]. As long as we know, there is no paper on the CNT reinforced rubber composite using DSC until now.

The objective of this study is to find out the relation between strain induced crystallization (SIC) and mechanical properties of CNT reinforced acrylonitrile butadiene rubber (NBR) composites with the atmospheric-pressure flame plasma (APFP) treatment, the acid treatment, and refluxing time.

2. Experimental Procedure

2.1 Materials Processing

The matrix for experimental works was a NBR. The reinforced carbon materials prepared for experiment

was multi-walled carbon nanotube (CM-100) from Hanwha Nanotech Co. Ltd. as shown in Table 1. The CNT was first chemically treated. One gram of CNT was chemically treated with 50ml solution (nitric acid (60%) 1: sulfuric acid (60%) 3) for 2hrs at 100°C. It was then filtered and washed with distilled water several times to remove the acid and dried in oven at 100°C. The plasma treatment of the CNT was carried out with an APFP treatment apparatus [7]. The dispersion of nano-tubes involves the dissolution of CNTs in a toluene in order to disentangle the nano-tubes that typically tend to cling together and form lumps, making it difficult to process. For this phase, 1g of CNTs was added to a 100 ml of toluene using a weighing balance. This solution was further sonicated for 1hr using a mechanical sonicator (Vibra Cell, Sonic & Material Co.), capable of vibrating at ultrasonic frequencies (750Watts, 20 kHz) in order to induce an efficient dispersion of CNTs.

Table 1 Compounding formulation

	Ingredients	Amount (phr)
Elastomer	35L	100.0
Activator	ZnO	5.0
	S-Acid	1.0
	CM-100	0, 3, 6, 9
Processing Oil	DOP	3.0
Accelerator	Oricell TT	1.2
	Vanax NS	2.0
	Sulfur	0.8
Vulcanizing Agent		

(phr: part per hundred grams of rubber)

Finally, to mix the CNT solution and rubber solution, the mixing machine (IKA Ultra-Turrax®, T-25 Digital) was used for 1hr at 10,000rpm. Then, the CNT/NBR dry mixture was obtained by evaporating the solvent off at 80°C under vacuum. At the end, the dried nanocomposite material was pressed using the hot press.

2.2 Measurement Method

The degree of crystallinity and glass transition temperature (T_g) of the sample was measured by differential scanning calorimeter (DSC Q200®, TA Instruments). The sample dried completely in vacuum oven was used for the analysis. The sample was heated from -80°C under a nitrogen atmosphere to 300°C at a rate of 10°C/min. Holders for stretched samples were machined from brass because of its high thermal diffusivity, high melting point, and low expansion. The degree of the stretch [8], defined as $\lambda = \frac{\text{length of uniaxially deformed specimen}}{\text{length of relaxed specimen}}$, was chosen to be $\lambda = 1$ (relaxed state), $\lambda = 1.5, 2, 2.5, \text{ and } 3$. The tensile properties were measured using an Autograph of the Shimadzu tensile machine (Model AG-5000E) with a testing speed of 50mm/min. The specimen geometry was a dumbbell shape (60×10×1mm) and cut from the cured plate. Typically, five specimens were used for a single evaluation.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Mechanical Properties

Many researchers have been studied the CNT reinforced natural rubber (NR) [2, 9-10]. However, the NR has a high electrical resistance material. Thus, we used the NBR as a pure matrix for development of low electrical resistance rubber composite in this study. The tensile properties of the composites are presented as functions of CNT content in Fig. 1. The tensile strength and modulus gradually increase as the amount of CNTs content. As the material extended, the separation between CNTs and matrix occurs, and finally fractures. Since the CNT has high aspect ratio and can be deformed in early stage of extension, the modulus of

Fig. 1 Effect of CNT volume content on the tensile properties

composites is sensitive than the strength of composites. The tensile strength and modulus increases up to 31%, and 91% compared to the matrix at the fiber content 9phr, respectively. Depending on the type of reinforcing fillers, the molecule orientation is different. The case of the CNT shows the clear molecule orientation because of its big aspect ratio.

To modify CNTs, the used chemical method is the acid treatment and the physical method is the APFP treatment. Due to the APFP, the CNT surface becomes a polarization, and is affected a surface density and an electron array. Figs. 2-3 show results for the tensile properties depending on the APFP treatment, acid treatment, and acid concentration. Through the acid process of CNT, a transition metal of CNT surface is removed and the dispersion characteristic of the compacted particles becomes better. However, the composites with acid treated CNT show lower tensile properties compared to the case without acid treatment. If the excessive energy is applied to the CNT, the length of CNT shortens and disperses uniformly, and the outer wall gets damaged. After all, the structural features of the nano-tube disappear. Therefore, the dispersion of CNT is improved, but the reinforcement of CNT is reduced. Also, the cases with the APFP treatment represent higher value compared to the case without the APFP treatment. It seems that the combination between the rubber and CNTs is improved because the amorphous carbon materials of CNT are pyrolyzed due to the high temperature of plasma [11]. Fig. 4 presents the SEM photograph of APFP

treated CNT. It is found that the end (\curvearrowright) in each tube has been deformed as a ball under the impact of high temperature.

To compare the effect of the acid concentration, the concentration of sulfuric acid (SA) is increased up to 90% while maintaining the concentration of nitric acid (NA). Also, the refluxing time is changed from 0 to 2 hrs. Figs. 5-6 depict results for the tensile properties at CNT content of 6phr. As the refluxing time increases from 0 to 2 hrs and the sulfuric-acid concentration increases from 60% to 90%, the tensile strength and modulus of these composites decrease.

Fig. 4 SEM photograph of 'P' treated CNT

Fig. 2 Effects of APFP('P') and acid('A') treatment on the tensile strength

Fig. 3 Effects of APFP('P') and acid('A') treatment on the tensile modulus

Fig. 5 Effects of acid concentration, Plasma treatment and refluxing time of CNT on the tensile strength

Fig. 6 Effects of acid concentration, plasma treatment and refluxing time of CNT on the tensile modulus

Fig. 1 Typical DSC curve of the matrix

Fig. 8 Effect of CNT content on the LHC

3.2 DSC Analysis

In order to further characterize the interactions between CNT and matrix, DSC measurement was conducted. DSC defines the glass transition as a change in the heat capacity when the polymer matrix goes from the glass state to the rubber state. This requires the heat to go through the transition, so in the DSC curve the transition appears as a step transition and not a peak such as might be seen with a crystalline region. Fig. 7 shows a typical DSC curve of the matrix. Fig. 8 indicates results for the latent heat for crystallization (LHC) at 1.5 extension ratio (λ). The crystallization enthalpy is calculated by integrating the heating power of the crystallization peak in time, divided by the sample mass. DSC analysis reveals that the degree of

Fig. 9 Effect of extension ratio on the LHC and Tg

Fig. 10 Effects of acid concentration, plasma treatment, and refluxing time of CNT on the LHC at CNT 6phr.

crystallinity of the composites increases with the increase of CNT content. The LHC of the matrix is 0.9 J/g. When the CNT content is 9 phr, the LHC is 4.48 J/g. As the extension ratio increases, the results of Tg and LHC are shown in Fig. 9 at CNT of 6phr. The Tg of the composite increases with the increase of λ , and LHC of that shows the maximum at $\lambda=1.5$. In general, the crystalline region is stronger than the amorphous region. Therefore, the increase of LHC means the reinforcing effect of composites and improves the mechanical properties. As shown in Figs. 1 and 8, the mechanical properties have a linear relation with the LHC depending on the CNT content. The tensile strength and modulus of composites increase with increasing the CNT content when compared to the matrix. Also, the LHC

shows the same trend and increases up to 5 times compared to the matrix at the fiber content 9 phr. Also, it is found that the T_g of the matrix is observed at -33.2°C, and that of CNT reinforced composites increases with increasing the extension ratio. Fig. 10 depicts results for the LHc at CNT content of 6phr. The LHc of composites shows the maximum value without acid treatment, and decreases as the refluxing time increases from 0 to 2 hr. and the sulfuric-acid concentration increases from 60% to 90%. In contrast, the case of the APFP treated specimen was higher than that of the untreated one.

4. Summary and Conclusions

The following conclusions can be drawn from this study.

- (1) The tensile strength and modulus increase with the increase of CNT content when compared to the matrix. The increasing ratio of the tensile modulus is higher than that of the tensile strength because of CNT orientation. And the tensile strength and modulus of composites with the CNT content of 9 phr increases up to 31% and 91%, respectively.
- (2) The composites with the APFP treated CNTs represent higher value compared to the case without the APFP treatment. However, the composites with the acid treated CNTs show a lower value compared to the case without the acid treatment.
- (3) As the refluxing time increases from 0 to 2 hr. and the sulfuric-acid concentration increases from 60% to 90%, the tensile strength and modulus of the composite decrease.
- (4) As the extension ratio increases, the T_g of the composite increases, and LHc of that shows the maximum at $\lambda=1.5$. And the mechanical properties have a linear relation with the LHc depending on the CNT content.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported by the Korea Science & Engineering Foundation (KOSEF) grant funded by the Korea government (MEST) (No.2009-0076679).

References

- [1] S. Iijima, *Nature*, 354, pp. 56-58, 1991.
- [2] A. Fakhru'l-Razi, M.A. Atieh, N. Girun, T.G. Chuah, M. El-Sadig, and D.R.A. Biak, *Composite Structures*, 75, pp. 496-500, 2006.
- [3] P. Verge, S. Peeterbroeck, L. Bonnaud, and P. Dubois, *Composite Science and Technology*, 70, pp. 1453-1459, 2010.
- [4] L. Lu, Y. Zhai, Y. Zhang, C. Ong, and S. Guo, *Applied Surface Science*, 255, pp. 2162-2166, 2008.
- [5] M. Baja, S.C. George, J.L. Gardette, and J. Lacoste, *Rubber Chem and Tech*, 75, p. 143, 2002.
- [6] A.K. Sircar, S. Rodrigues, and R.P. Chartoff, *Rubber Chem and Tech*, 72, p. 513, 1999.
- [7] J.H. Sung, D.J. Lee and S.R. Ryu, "Mechanical properties of elastomeric composites with atmospheric pressure flame plasma treated multi-walled carbon nano-tube and carbon black", *Proceedings of ACCM7*, Taiwan, paper No. TUE-SE02-06, 2010.
- [8] Lyon RE, Farris RJ, MacKnight WJ, *J of Polym Sci, Polym Lettes*, Ed 21, 323-328, 1983.
- [9] Sanjib, B., Christophe, S., Ouziyine, B., Marie-Louise, S., Sabu, T. and Jean-Paul, S., *Carbon*, 46, pp. 1037-1045, 2008.
- [10] Sui, G., Zhong, W. H., Yang, X. P. and Yu, Y. H., *Mater Sci and Eng A*, 485, pp. 524-531, 2008.
- [11] Kim, D. O. and Nam, J. D., *Prospectives of Industrial Chemistry*, 9(6), pp. 3-13, 2006.